

THE PROBLEMS THAT PRE-SCHOOL TEACHERS' ENCOUNTER

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to identify problems such as administration, program and parental issues that pre-school teachers encounter. The other purpose is to investigate whether the teacher perceptions on problems that pre-school teachers encounter differ statistically significantly depending on the presence of a helper in the class, school building type and the economic status of the neighborhood in which the school located. This is a survey study, and the Problems of Pre-School Teachers Scale was developed as the data collection tool of the study. The population of this study is composed of 329 teachers who work in the center of Şanlıurfa, Turkey during 2012-2013 fall semesters. The study is conducted with the participation of 220 teachers selected via simple random sampling method. The exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses, t test and one-way analysis of variance methods were used. The findings indicate that there are significant differences in the perceptions of pre-school teachers related to administration, program and parents. These were discussed along with literature support and recommendations to school administrators were generated.

Keywords: pre-school teacher, administration, parent, program

1. Introduction

Pre-school education refers to the education process that children- from birth to the beginning of primary school- are provided appropriate to their individual characteristics and developmental level in a rich stimulating environment with opportunities to help them develop in accordance with the community's cultural values and properties (Poyraz & Dere, 2003, p. 21). Early childhood education is a critical

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period for the development of the brain. Studies show that the most important part of brain development occurs in the first six years. 3-6 years is the period in which the connections between neurons occur at the highest level. When an infant reaches the age of three, the physical growth of the brain is 90% completed. Childhood experiences determine which brain cells are used in brain's working circuits. It has been proved that life and environmental conditions of the childhood affect brain function in a positive or negative way, and the brain development of the children who don't play games or were touched very few is 20-30% less than their peers (Nash, 1997). For this reason, providing children with opportunities for complex detection and physical experience affects the development of learning skills in a positive way for years to come. Even the provision of such facilities can compensate for the lack of early nutritional deficiencies or at least may resolve to some extent (Bekman, 1999).

The importance of early childhood education on educational process, adult life, the development of family and community is appreciated better than in the past by everyone (Yapıcı & Ulu, 2010). Therefore, early childhood education has become a priority in the agenda of nations as well as international organizations. Many international organizations such as World Bank, UNICEF, the United Nations, the World Health Organization produce policies regarding early childhood education, provide financial resources and work on the implementation of them. International organizations dealing with early childhood education, while adopting institutional and home-based models, support the models that are more flexible and cost efficient especially for children and families in poor areas who need more educational support.

The teacher is the central element of the learning process (Akgün, Yazar & Dinçer, 2011). There is a significant relationship between the quality of the educators and the school itself (Uşun & Cömert, 2003). For the sake of the quality and affectivity of an education system, teachers should be encouraged to continually renew and enrich their knowledge. Teachers are expected to adopt new roles and become friends who play, sings, shares joy and sorrow of their students. During pre-school period, the inborn features of the child's, shaped by the influence of his environment, makes up his personality and It is generally accepted that children in their process of the formation of their personalities, constantly need a model to copy the behaviors and personal features and identify themselves with. Therefore, as a role model for the children, teachers need to pay attention to their appearance, behaviors and thoughts and accept the children as an individual (Aral, Kandır, Yaşar, 2002). This model for children in pre-school education is the teacher (Öztürk & Deniz, 2008). The pre-school teacher who is in interaction with the child all day long makes a personality model for the child. Therefore, the qualifications of a preschool teacher are very important for the child

(Üstünoğlu, 1993). However, the preschool teacher's job is complex and demanding (Alison & Berthelsen, 1995).

Considering above-mentioned and expected qualifications of pre-school teachers, it is clear how great and how difficult their jobs are. Also, because of the social change and other stressors such as school administration, workload, parental pressure and etc., teachers come face to face with increased paternal and community expectations for the outcomes and standards of education (Alison & Berthelsen, 1995). Preschool teachers are crucial for teaching moral and other values (Prochner, Cleghorn, Kirova & Massing, 2014) but as stated above their professional life could be filled with plenty of stressors. The stressors for teachers in the preschool environment could be time pressures, children's needs, non-teaching tasks, maintaining early childhood philosophy and practice, personal needs, issues with parents of the children, interpersonal relationships, attitudes and perceptions about early childhood programs (Alison & Berthelsen, 1995).

They are also responsible for the health, safety, education and the development of the children in his group as well as the child's attending school happily. In addition to all these, a pre-school teacher is to respond to the needs and expectations of the parents of children; to establish an effective communication between school administration and other staff; to prepare and follow proper training programs with all details; and to attend in-service training for self-improvement. They are believed to play a critical role in promoting socially accepted behaviors and reducing unwanted behaviors in their students (Anderson, 2013). Thus, it is a must to provide a pre-school teacher with all the support and conditions in work place as well as understating, psychological support (Budunç, 2007, p. 4).

It is generally agreed that the wellbeing of preschool teachers is important for promoting a positive academic and psycho-social development of the children (Allenworth & Kolbe, 1987). Well educated preschool teachers are essential to provide high quality early childhood education in preschools (OECD, 2012). The quality of the education that a pre-school teacher offers to a child is also considered to be strictly connected with the experience of teacher, the working environment and living conditions (Gömleksiz & Serhatlıoğlu, 2013). The quality of the education may be affected by working environment in a positive or negative way depending upon satisfaction or stress at workplace. Especially, various needs of the children and families, challenges of the work, lack of time to take care of each child individually are some of the important factors affecting the quality of work done by the preschool teachers (Helsing, 2007; Sheridan 2007). Besides, preschool teachers are both classroom instructors and in-home child care providers. Such a status may make them more sensible to the problems of the children under the teacher's care (Jeon, Buettner & Snyder, 2014). Furthermore, spending more time in low quality classrooms leads to

increased behavioral problems among children in preschools (McCartney et al., 2010; Zhai, Raver & Li-Grining, 2011).

Apart from the issues related to technical core in the kindergarten social system, there is another difference which makes kindergarten has a unique nature. It is the organizational structure of kindergarten which is very simple and loosely coupled when compared to the higher level of educational institutions. Simple and loosely coupled organizations are expected to have cozy interactions among personnel, and open climate. Hence, the characteristics of the work environment of the kindergarten may provide different opportunities or create different problems for teachers. Concerning the different organizational structure of kindergarten, the teacher's interaction with the parents and school administration may work differently. And this may create different problems in kindergarten when compared to the higher level of educational institutions. Thus, it can be determined what factors in the working environment may affect the education that the pre-school teacher gives to the children. In literature, there seems to be enough study regarding the pre-school applications, this study will focus on the administrative, program and parental problems that a preschool teacher may encounter.

In Turkey, preschool education is considered to have many problems. Previous research investigated these problems like classroom management (Akgün, Yazar & Dinçer, 2011), work environment (Budunç, 2007), self-efficacy beliefs (Gömleksiz & Serhatlıoğlu, 2013), work satisfaction and burnout (Öztürk & Deniz, 2008), professional development (Uşun & Cömert, 2003) and quality (Üstünoğlu, 1993). However, problems regarding to administration, program and parental issues had never been investigated. Therefore, the characteristics of the work environment must be determined. Thus, it can be determined what factors in the working environment may affect the education that the pre-school teacher gives to the children. Besides, the teacher's interaction with the parents and school administration may affect the performance of the teacher. In literature, there seems to be enough study regarding the pre-school applications, this study will focus on the administrative, program and parental problems that a preschool teacher may encounter.

The purpose of this study is to identify the problems that preschool teachers working in Şanlıurfa city center encounter in terms of administration, program and parental issues. The outcomes of this study would be helpful in modifying school administration and program and in making recommendation to education of parents.

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the levels of the problems regarding administration, program and the parents that pre-school teachers face?

2. Do the problems that pre-school teachers face differ significantly depending on the type of school, the presence of a helper, socio-economic level of the location?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This study was designed as a survey research. This research is based on collecting data from large samples, so generalization of the findings can be meaningful (Fraenkel, Wallen & Hyun, 2012).

2.2. Participants

The population of this study is the pre-school teachers who work in the center of Şanlıurfa, Turkey during 2012-2013 fall semesters. There were 329 teachers in the population of this study. In the study, due to lack of time, the sampling from the population was employed. A sample of maximum 217 (%5 confidence interval and level of 5% error tolerance) from the population that consists of a total 329 people has been found to representative (Balci, 1997, p. 112). However, researcher, taking the problems that may be encountered while administrating the questionnaires and possible losses in collection into account, takes the sampling size as 71% and determines about 220. For the collection of research data questionnaire was administered to 240 pre-school teachers and 220 analyses was conducted because 20 of them were considered invalid. Sampling model as "simple random sampling" approach has been adopted (Büyüköztürk et al., 2010, p. 84).

2.3. Instrument

For this study, a valid and reliable measurement tool to determine the problems regarding administration, program and the parents that pre-school teachers may face was developed (See appendix). The measurement tool consists of two parts and the first part involves personal data relating to pre-school teachers while second part involves problem statements related to management, program and the parents. For the content validity, a questionnaire consisting of 34 items was prepared. During the development of the questionnaire, domestic and foreign literature were examined, with the help of the information obtained, the questionnaire was designed as to include the problems regarding to management, program and parent that the pre-school teachers have. Expert opinion to determine the validity of the measurement tool has been applied. Before the exploratory factor analysis Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy value was calculated as .89. The value should be closer to 1 so that the relationship between variables and factor analysis can be said to provide reliable results

(Field, 2000). Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant meaning that data were suitable for factor analysis ($p < .05$). After the exploratory factor analysis, 9 items were removed and 25 items remained in the final questionnaire under 3 sub factors explaining 52% of total variance (see appendix). Sub factors had Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients ranging from $\alpha = .77$ to $\alpha = .90$ (Table 1). The resulting scale was named as the problems of pre-school teachers scale.

Table 1: Exploratory factor analysis results

Factors	Items	Factor Loadings	Alpha	Variance %
Management	12	.45-.79	.84	21.3
Parents	10	.55-.85	.90	22.3
Program	3	.72-.78	.77	8.5
Total	25	.45-.85	.90	52.1

To confirm the factor structure revealed by the exploratory factor analysis, a confirmatory factor analysis was also conducted using Lisrel 8.8 packet software. To decide whether the factor structure is consistent with different factor analysis methods, model fit indexes were used as criteria. These indexes along with their acceptable value ranges are presented in the Table 2 below.

Table 2: Confirmatory factor analysis results

Fit Indexes	Excellent Fit Criteria	Acceptable Fit Criteria	Actual Values	Result
X^2/df (CMIN/DF)	$0 \leq X^2/df \leq 2$	$2 \leq X^2/df \leq 3$	1.91	Excellent Fit
GFI	$.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	$.80 \leq GFI \leq .95$	0.83	Acceptable Fit
CFI	$.95 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$.90 \leq CFI \leq .95$	0.96	Excellent Fit
NNFI	$.95 \leq TLI \leq 1.00$	$.90 \leq TLI \leq .95$	0.96	Excellent Fit
IFI	$.95 \leq IFI \leq 1.00$	$.90 \leq IFI \leq .95$	0.96	Excellent Fit
RMSEA	$.00 \leq RMSEA \leq .05$	$.05 \leq RMSEA \leq .08$	0.07	Acceptable Fit
SRMR	$.00 \leq SRMR \leq .05$	$.05 \leq SRMR \leq .10$	0.06	Acceptable Fit

Resource: (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu & Büyüköztürk, 2014; Hu & Bentler, 1999).

2.4. Data Analysis

For the analysis and evaluation of research findings, SPSS and AMOS statistical software were used. For analysis, $p = .05$ level is taken as a basis. Since the data were distributed normally ($n=220$, Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic=.045, $p > .05$), parametric statistics were used. The exploratory factor analysis was done to reveal the factor structure of the developed instrument. Then the confirmatory factor analysis was used to test the revealed factor structure. Finally, independent groups t test and one-way

analysis of variance were used to reveal statistically significant differences according to type of school, the presence of a helper and socio-economic level of the location.

3. Results

Below are the findings from the t-test analysis of preschool teachers' ideas regarding to management, program and parents sub factors in the cases of having an independent building and existing within the elementary school building.

Table 3: Results from the t-test analysis of preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the management sub factor

Variable	Level	n	$\bar{X}$	Sd	df	t	p
School Building	Independent Preschool	108	3.52	.76	203	8.22	.000*
	Within Element. School	97	2.69	.68			

*p<.001

According to Table 3, a difference existed between teachers' school level with a significance found at the $p < .001$ level. Preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the management sub factor differentiated between the school levels ($t_{203} = 8.22$ $p < .001$). Independent preschool teachers appreciate school management more positively ($\bar{X} = 3.52$) than their colleagues ($\bar{X} = 2.69$) working within elementary schools.

Table 4: Results from the t-test analysis of preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the program sub factor

Variable	Level	n	$\bar{X}$	Sd	df	t	p
School Building	Independent Preschool	108	4.04	.72	203	2.52	.012*
	Within Element. School	97	3.76	.56			

*p<.05

According to Table 4, preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the program sub factor differentiated between the school levels ($t_{203} = 2.52$ $p < .005$). Independent preschool teachers appreciate program more positively ($\bar{X} = 4.04$) than their colleagues ($\bar{X} = 3.76$) working within elementary schools.

Table 5: Findings from the t-test analysis of preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the parents sub factor

Variable	Level	n	$\bar{X}$	Sd	df	t	p
School Building	Independent Preschool	108	2.82	.78	203	2.12	.035*
	Within Element. School	97	2.58	.86			

*p<.05

According to Table 5, preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the parents sub factor differentiated between the school levels ($t_{203} = 2.12$ $p < .005$). Independent preschool teachers appreciate parents more positively ($\bar{x} = 2.82$) than their colleagues ($\bar{x} = 2.58$) working within elementary schools.

Below are the findings from the ANOVA of preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the management sub factor in the cases of classroom assistant type and social economic status (SES) of the school community. Tukey HSD test findings for differentiated groups are also presented.

Preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the management sub factor differentiated among the assistant types [$F_{3,204} = 18.091$; $p < .001$] and among the community SES [$F_{2,204} = 37.218$; $p < .05$]. To identify differences between groups Tukey test is conducted and results suggest that differences are between 1 and 4, 2 and 4, 3 and 4 for the assistant type level. Therefore, mean of the ideas of those who had assistant sisters is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 3.22$) than those of who had none ($\bar{x} = 2.62$). Also, mean of the ideas of those who had interns is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 3.08$) than those of who had none ($\bar{x} = 2.62$). Finally, mean of the ideas of those who had both type of assistants is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 3.70$) than those of who had none ($\bar{x} = 2.62$).

Table 6: Results from the ANOVA of preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the management sub factor

Variable	Level	n	$\bar{x}$	Sd	df	F	p	Tukey HSD
Assistant Type	1.Assistant Sister	66	3.22	.74	3.204	18.091	.000*	1-4, 2-4, 3-4
	2.Intern	37	3.08	.67				
	3.Both	44	3.70	.75				
	4.None	58	2.62	.79				
Community SES	1.High Level	63	3.67	.66	2.204	37.218	.000**	1-3,2-3
	2.Medium Level	64	3.22	.77				
	3.Low Level	78	3.13	.72				

* $p < .05$

Tukey test for the community SES level suggest that differences are between 1 and 3, 2 and 3. Therefore mean of the ideas of those whose schools are in high SES communities is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 3.67$) than those of whose schools are in low SES communities ($\bar{x} = 3.13$). Also, mean of the ideas of those whose schools are in medium SES communities is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 3.22$) than those of whose schools are in low SES communities ($\bar{x} = 3.13$).

Table 7: Results from the ANOVA of preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the program sub factor

Variable	Level	n	$\bar{X}$	Sd	df	F	p	Tukey HSD
Assistant Type	1.Assistant Sister	66	4.046	.820	3.204	8.421	.000*	1-4, 2-4, 3-4
	2.Intern	37	4.072	.667				
	3.Both	44	4.121	.667				
	4.None	58	3.489	.795				
Community SES	1.High Level	63	4.011	.752	2.204	.866	.030*	1-3,2-3
	2.Medium Level	64	3.901	.702				
	3.Low Level	78	3.833	.899				

*p<.05

Preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the program sub factor differentiated among the assistant types [$F_{3,204}=8.421$; $p<.05$] and among the community SES [$F_{2,204}=.866$; $p<.05$]. To identify differences between groups Tukey test is conducted and results suggest that differences are between 1 and 4, 2 and 4, 3 and 4 for the assistant type level. Therefore, mean of the ideas of those who had assistant sisters is significantly higher ($\bar{X}= 4.046$) than those of who had none ($\bar{X}= 3.489$). Also, mean of the ideas of those who had interns is significantly higher ($\bar{X}= 4.072$) than those of who had none ($\bar{X}= 3.489$). Finally, mean of the ideas of those who had both type of assistants is significantly higher ($\bar{X}= 4.121$) than those of who had none ($\bar{X}= 3.489$).

Tukey test for the community SES level suggest that differences are between 1 and 3, 2 and 3. Therefore mean of the ideas of those whose schools are in high SES communities is significantly higher ($\bar{X}= 4.011$) than those of whose schools are in low SES communities ($\bar{X}= 3.833$). Also, mean of the ideas of those whose schools are in medium SES communities is significantly higher ($\bar{X}= 3.901$) than those of whose schools are in low SES communities ($\bar{X}= 3.833$).

Table 8: Results from the ANOVA of preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the parents sub factor

Variable	Level	n	$\bar{X}$	Sd	df	F	P	Tukey HSD
Assistant Type	1.Assistant Sister	66	2.818	.879	3.204	8.816	.000*	1-4, 2-4, 3-4
	2.Intern	37	2.651	.657				
	3.Both	44	3.204	.725				
	4.None	58	2.400	.835				
Community SES	1.High Level	63	3.170	.804	2.204	25.86	.000**	1-3,2-3
	2.Medium Level	64	2.911	.780				
	3.Low Level	78	2.286	.694				

*p<.05

Preschool teachers' ideas regarding to the parents sub factor differentiated among the assistant types [$F_{3,204}=8.816$; $p<.05$] and among the community SES [$F_{2,204}=25.86$; $p<.05$]. To identify differences between groups Tukey test is conducted and results suggest that differences are between 1 and 4, 2 and 4, 3 and 4 for the assistant type level. Therefore, mean of the ideas of those who had assistant sisters is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 2.818$) than those of who had none ($\bar{x} = 2.400$). Also, mean of the ideas of those who had interns is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 2.651$) than those of who had none ($\bar{x} = 2.400$). Finally, mean of the ideas of those who had both type of assistants is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 3.204$) than those of who had none ($\bar{x} = 2.400$).

Tukey test for the community SES level suggest that differences are between 1 and 3, 2 and 3. Therefore, mean of the ideas of those whose schools are in high SES communities is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 3.170$) than those of whose schools are in low SES communities ($\bar{x} = 2.286$). Also, mean of the ideas of those whose schools are in medium SES communities is significantly higher ($\bar{x} = 2.911$) than those of whose schools are in low SES communities ($\bar{x} = 2.286$).

Table 9: Levels of the factors

Factors	$\bar{x}$	Std. Deviation
Program	3.90	.79
Total	3.26	.64
Management	3.12	.83
Parents	2.75	.84

Levels of the problems regarding to management, program and parents that pre-school teachers face are presented above in Table 9. Findings indicate that since the program factor has the highest mean scores, the least problems existed in the program factor ($\bar{x} = 3.90$) at a few levels. Total scores of the whole scale ($\bar{x} = 3.26$) imply that teachers face pre-school education problems at a medium level. Also, problems related to the management factor ($\bar{x} = 3.12$) are experienced at a medium level too. The most problematic area for teachers is the parents' factor. Mean scores of the parents factor ($\bar{x} = 2.75$) indicate that problems are experienced at a medium level but more frequently than other factors.

4. Discussion & Conclusion

The teachers who are working at independent kindergarten assess the school management more positively when compared to their colleagues who are working at state primary schools. This could be because when the nursery school is independent; that the number of students, teachers and staff is little and the focus is just on one

developmental stage (3-6) may lead to little workload for the school management. This may mean a better communication between management and preschool teacher. Just the opposite, when kindergarten is a part of primary school, that the number of students, teachers, staff and the variety of branches and students may lead too much workload for the school management. This could affect the communication between management and pre-school teachers. These implications are supported by various research findings (Büte & Balcı, 2010; Hoş, 2015; Karaküçük, 2008; Yaman, 2006; Öğülmüş & Özdemir, 1995).

Pre-school teachers that work at independent kindergartens assess the program and parents more positively than those who work at kindergartens as part of primary schools. This could be because of conscious and responsive parents prefer to send their children to have pre-school education at independent kindergartens, separate from the primary school building (Akkaya, 2007; Arnas, 2002; Çakmak, 2010; Ülkü, 2007; Zembat, 2012). Also, various research indicates that teachers' perceptions on program dimension may differ according to school type (Özsirkıntı, Cenk & Bolat, 2014; Sapsağlam, 2013).

Teachers' opinions about the administration vary depending on the type of people who work with them. According to this, the mean of the points of those who have a trainee, a helper or both together was found higher than those who don't have such help. Teachers' opinions on the program of schools vary depending on the type of people working in as well. According to this, the points of those who have a trainee, a helper or both together were found higher than those who don't have such help. Also, teachers' perceptions on parents vary depending on the type of people working with them. According to this, the points of those who have a trainee, a helper or both together were found higher than those who don't have such help. These could be because the less workload of the teacher may lead to less burnout (Bolat, 2011; Budak & Sürgevil, 2013). Because of less workload, teacher gets less tired and this could be the reason for the higher points on the items on the study regarding the interaction between school administrations. Also, this could be the reason for not making the program of the school a big deal. Teachers who don't have any sort of help in the class will have lots of workload and this may lead them to experience burn out. Besides, heavy work load will have a negative effect on how they view the school. This may be the reason why the points regarding school's program are low. Besides, heavy work load will have a negative effect on the communication between teachers and school administrations (Etme, 2009). Thus, the points regarding school administration will be low. Because of less workload, teacher gets less tired and this could be the reason for the higher points on the items regarding the interaction between parents (Çelenk, 2003). If the pre-school teachers' workload is too much and they don't have any help, their opinions related to

school administration, parent and program may be negative and this may cause more problems. In this regard, that pre-school teachers' workload is too much, they cannot have breaks thus this can increase professional burnout and that can lead to an increase in the occupational problems. Therefore, it should be made compulsory for administrators to provide someone to help each pre-school teacher in class.

Teachers' perceptions about the administration of the school vary depending on the socio-economic level of the location of the school. It has been found that regarding the administration, the mean points of the teachers who work at schools located in middle and upper socio-economic level districts are higher than those who work at schools located in low socio-economic level. This could be because the educational needs of teachers are provided very quickly by the administration. This could be because the school fees are paid by the parents regularly because the schools are located in good socio-economic level districts and parents are conscious about the importance of education (Özabacı & Acat, 2005). Thus, in this case, this may lead to a better interaction and relation between pre-school teacher and school administration (Biber, 2003).

Teachers' opinions on the program vary depending on the level of district in where the school is located. The study shows that teachers who work in schools located in middle and high socio-economic level districts give higher points on the questions asking their opinion on the program of the school than those who work in schools located in low socio-economic level districts. This could be because the better socio-economic level of the school means better program they have. High and regularly paid school fees enable school administration to develop better programs (Şahin & Kalburan, 2009; Taner & Başal, 2005). This may change the preschool teachers' opinions regarding school's program in a positive way.

Teachers' opinions about the parents of the students vary depending on the socio-economic level of the district in where school is located. The study shows that the mean of the points of teachers who work in schools located in middle and high districts are higher on the questions asking their opinion on the program of the school than those who are working in schools located in low socio-economic level districts. This could be because the schools that have better socio-economic levels have parents who are more conscious about the education and more interested in their children (Kotaman, 2008). In addition, they provide their children with everything they need, pay the school fee regularly. This enables parents to provide the preschool teachers with what they lack as soon as possible. This may be the reason for a better and higher level of relation between parents and the preschool teachers (Selimhocaoglu, 2016).

The outcomes of this study would be helpful in developing and modifying pre-school programs. Pre-school programs should consider the problems found in this

study. They should provide discretion to pre-school teachers to help overcome the problems. Especially providing an in-class helper would be a significant step in helping teachers reduces workload and burnout. In this manner, school administrators should take precautions to help teachers overcome the problems and reduce workload. The education of parents would make a huge improvement in the interaction between teachers and parents. Findings indicate its importance especially in the low socio-economic situations.

In this regard, there may be some suggestions in academic, organizational and political level. With the increasing importance of the preschool education either globally or locally, researchers should be aware of the structures and processes in kindergarten. When compared to the high schools, middle or primary schools, kindergarten is a simple organization which requires more loosely coupled structure allowing high teacher autonomy and efficiency. The informal side of the organization works different in kindergarten than the higher educational institutions. In such an organizational structure motivation of teachers are more effective on their productivity. This quantitative research presents a general view on the informal side of kindergarten by focusing on the problems of teachers. Hence, researches should study kindergarten deeply, especially by using qualitative research techniques offering deep insights in different cases.

At organizational level, especially principals of the kindergarten located in primary schools, should be more careful about their teachers' motivation. The results of the heavy workload and strict hierarchy may turn into teacher burn out. Concerning the loosely coupled structure of the kindergarten, principals should be more supportive for teachers to increase professional capacity and collaboration. Kindergarten enable the principals to give chance to teachers to reveal their leadership capabilities because of their loosely coupled nature. This may also increase teacher collaboration and motivation.

In accordance with the results of this study, some precautions should be taken at political level for the sake of effective preschool education. Educational policies should be supported by the social policies for kindergarten located in low socio-economic areas. This may decrease the financial burden on the families and may increase their participation to the school. Some additional gaining may also be effective to increase teacher commitment in kindergarten located in low socio-economic areas. Especially more autonomy and supportive work conditions may be provided with the law in kindergarten operating within primary schools. This may also helpful for dealing with needs of students, not the hierarchical problems of the primary school.

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Appendix: The Problems of Pre-School Teachers Scale

1. Our school makes necessary arrangements for students' regular and healthy nutrition.
2. In our school, there is a rich library that includes publications about pre-school education.
3. I communicate effectively with school administration to improve pre-school education.
4. Principal hosts meetings with pre-school teachers regularly and values our opinions.
5. Our school organizes cultural activities like trips, art activities etc. with pre-school teachers regularly.
6. In pre-school education, toilets and washbasins are adequate to meet children quantities.
7. In pre-school education classrooms, equipment like cupboards, coat racks, activity desks, chairs etc. are adequate to meet children quantities.
8. Size of the school garden, game tools and equipment are of adequate size and quantity for pre-school education.
9. In pre-school education, common grounds like refectory and toilets are cleaned regularly and adequately.
10. Our pre-school education classrooms located independently from primary education buildings.
11. Cognitive, affective and psychomotor activities organized for the development of pre-school education children are of adequate level.
12. Procurement of tools and equipment to meet the goals of pre-school education places pecuniary burden on parents.
13. The pre-school education program is adequate to children's level.
14. The pre-school education program directs children to make communication and collaboration.
15. The pre-school education meets interests and needs of children.
16. Parents help teachers in education activities in our school.
17. Families actively support the school to solve problems of pre-school education.
18. In pre-school education, parents bring their children to school and take them in a timely manner.
19. In pre-school education, parents meet the needs of students adequately and in a timely manner.
20. In pre-school education, parents get help from school to correct unwanted child behavior at home.

21. Parents show necessary importance to preparation of child's nutrition and to meal day duties.
22. In pre-school education, parents take care of their children adequately and value them.
23. In pre-school education, parents place necessary importance not to grow their children as spoiled but as accommodating.
24. In pre-school education, parents behave moderately in buying toys and gifts to their children.
25. In pre-school education, parents are against to violence in child education.

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